

Annex 3. Photographs illustrating the variability of WLI interfaces across continents

Europe

Figure 1. Examples of potential interactions between pigs and livestock in different habitats and husbandry regimes over Europe. Wild boar are probably one of the most relevant target species for integrated disease surveillance in Europe and, eventually, for targeted disease control interventions at the interface (e.g. Classical swine fever, African swine fever, tuberculosis). The left column represents the animals, and the right one, the habitat they inhabit, respectively. (a-b) Domestic pig foraging free on alpine pasture in the French Pyrenees close to the Spanish border. Free-range pig husbandry occurs in many European countries. This is a risk for disease transmission. (c-d) Direct contact between wild boar and pigs in South Central Spain, where Iberian pigs typically graze savanna-like habitat conformed by oaks (dehesas) during the mast season. (e-f) Indirect interaction between extensively reared pigs and wild boar in Sardinia Island (image A. Pintore). (g-h) Indirect interaction between wild boar and cattle in Doñana National Park (Southwest Spain) in pasturelands associated to the marsh-woodlands ecotone.

Figure 2. Examples of indirect interactions in Mediterranean livestock extensive systems (a) in a waterer and (b) a seasonal stream, involving wild boar and red deer, the most widely distributed wild ungulates over the continent (together with roe deer). Pigs, cattle, and goats are observed. The need to identify interactions with the potential for pathogen transmission among the community of hosts at the wildlife-livestock interface has led to the use of multiple methodologies, such as camera trapping (Images: Joaquín Vicente).

Figure 3. Wildlife reservoirs harbour microbial organisms or parasites that are mostly commensals or non-pathogenic in the wild reservoir but became pathogenic for domestic species and eventually humans, and *vice versa*. Some pathogens adapted to the human, the wildlife or the domestic compartment, respectively, may be transmitted between these compartments thanks to bridge hosts species, such as domesticated animals or peri domestic wildlife. The white stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) is a traditional trans-Saharan migrant in Europe. Recently, storks have adapted to rubbish dumps (a-b) as reliable food source and have reduced migratory distance or become sedentary. (b) White stork interacting with cattle at water source (pond) in central Spain. (c) The cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) is a cosmopolitan species of heron, originally native to parts of Asia, Africa, and Europe which has undergone a rapid expansion in its distribution. The image illustrates some individuals scavenging on discarded eggs (normally broken) in the periphery of a hen farm. (d) House sparrows (*Passer domesticus*) may bring health hazards to poultry facilities. The image was taken in backyard hen holding (note the unusual presence of a semi-domesticated roe deer). Images: courtesy of U. Höfle.

Asia

Figure 4. Asia is very diverse, not only in terms of habitats and wildlife communities, but socioeconomical contexts and wildlife management. More developed countries, such as in other parts of the North hemisphere (Europe, North America) have experienced decrease in anthropogenic pressures on wildlife during the last decades (e.g., hunting and habitat alteration), and certain species may benefit, like wild ungulates. As wildlife recovery, human–wildlife conflict increases. (a, b) Rural landscapes in Japan integrated in the “recovered” nature. (b) The segregation of wildlife and human uses is becoming a problem. Protection in crops against wild ungulates in Hokkaido Island (Japan) where its natural predator, the wolf, is extinct. (c-d) Yezo sika deer (*Cervus nippon yezoensis*) in proximity to human activities (Hokkaido Island, Japan) (images: J. Vicente). (e-f) triple human-wildlife-livestock interface examples in Nepal (images: C. Gortázar).

Africa

of animals and humans. This congregation will increase with climate change (Photo: B. Faye). Wildlife interactions in rural areas of Africa are common through hunting or by keeping wildlife as pets. Wildlife utilisation activities have developed in Africa in recent years. Different forms of wildlife exploitation such as cane rat farming in West Africa and the bushmeat trade have been expanding during recent decades in different parts of Africa and generating new forms of interface between wild animals and human environment (Photos: Ferran Jori). Wildlife management skills lack in many African countries. High wildlife management and capture skills are very efficient to monitor the health of wildlife populations. However, they are only available in a minority of countries in East and West Africa, where the wildlife industry contributes substantially to the national economies. Most African countries lack this kind of expertise, which is out of their financial reach. Innovative and cheaper ways to obtain wildlife health information are needed (Photos: Ferran Jori).

Oceania

Figure 6. A horse being tested for Hendra virus in Australia (left panel) and fruit bats the primary host of a lethal zoonotic virus (right panel). Feral pigs near cattle in Australia and direct contact between brushtailed possums and cattle in New Zealand. Introduced cattle (*Bos taurus*) and rusa deer (*Timorensis rusa*) frequently interact within pastures in New Caledonia. Photo: Nicolas Barré. Wild boar from Central Spain (left) and wild pig from Molokai (right, Hawaii).

North America

Figure 7. Here pictured with a dairy cow, white-tailed deer are a primary species of wildlife at the interface with livestock in North America. Blackbirds feeding with dairy cattle in southwestern United States. Photos: USDA/APHIS/Wildlife Services. Raccoon (*Procyon lotor*) and white-tailed deer visiting resources meant cattle.

Figure 8. Example of livestock and wildlife use of a protein feeder in south Texas. Source: Anonymous private ranch in south Texas.

South America

Figure 9. (a-b) Camera trappings of cattle and ocelot (*Leopardus pardalis*) in the same spot in Ecuador. Tropical forests are increasingly destroyed to clear land that is ultimately used for beef production, making beef the largest driver of tropical deforestation globally. (c) There are vast forested areas at risk of conversion for pastureland expansion in South America. The picture shows a cleared area where black vultures (*Coragyps atratus*) wait for cows to defecate and/or give birth to feed on faecal and reproductive mucosae and tissues. (d) The capybara (*Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris*) is the largest living rodent in the world a large rodent native to South America (Image: Daniel Ortega, Venezolano, Creative Commons CC0 License), living near bodies of water in savannas and dense forests. The capybara is a potential reservoir for *Trypanosoma evansi*, that causes one form of surra in animals. (e) Vicuña (*Vicugna vicugna*) in Chimborazo (Ecuador). The vicuña is one of the two wild South American camelids which live in the high alpine areas of the Andes, the other being the guanaco. Vicuñas are the wild ancestor of domesticated alpacas. Sheep (f) was introduced to South America for extensive cattle ranching, occupying the same habitat as camelids (vicuña and guanaco- *Lama guanicoe*, see also next figure).

Figure 10. (a) The greater rhea (*Rhea americana*) is a South American ratite endemic to Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay. The image shows a close interaction with cattle, very different (phylogenetically) species (image: M. M. Guerisoli-Grupo de Ecología Comportamental de Mamíferos). (b) These images illustrate the human face of the triple human-wildlife-livestock interface; a peccary piglet is fed by a local villager in proximity of domestic pets and poultry in Perú (images: C. Gortazar). (c-e) Livestock, such as horses, and guanacos (*Lama guanicoe*) and huemules (*Hippocamelus bisulcus*) share habitat in the Magallanes Region (Torres del Paine National Park, Chile) (images: Ezequiel Hidalgo). The guanaco is the wild ancestor of the llama and inhabits the Andean and Patagonian steppes from sea level to high altitudes. (f) Pudu (*Pudu pudu*) and cattle sharing habitat at the Nahuelbuta National Park of the Bio Bio Region in Chile (images: Dario Moreira Arce). (g) Wild-domestic carnivore interaction illustrated by American sea lions (*Otaria flavescens*) and dogs in the Perú coast (image: C. Gortazar).